

"CONCEPT" IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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In recent years, cognitive science has developed rapidly. Development is also a concept concept in linguistic studies caused the problem to become more urgent. Because cognitive based on the approach of a linguist-researcher, it is through language that a person is cognitive understands the mechanism. This is the whole level, system of the language factual information with new conclusions makes it possible to enrich. Human intelligence, laws of thought with the ancient sciences of logic, philosophy, physiology, psychology has been engaged in. Also with the theory of consciousness in philosophy there is a separate department dealing with it - epistemology. For this reason it can be said that cognitivism is related to the philosophy of antiquity has a tradition. In today's cognitive science, there are old issues it can be observed that it is being interpreted in a new way.

Keywords: concept; cognitivism; cognitive mechanism; knowing; a person factor; human intelligence; cognitive psychology; conceptual analysis; cultural anthropology; modeling of artificial intelligence; neuroscience; linguistics; gestalt; frame.

Cognitive linguistics (cognitive linguistics; linguistic; linguistique cognitive) is a new direction of linguistics and its focus is on the information formation of language and information plays an important role in the transition to (encoded) expression-representation there is a question of studying general cognitive mechanisms. This system is one opposite to other semiotic tools of humanity is placed and at the same time, independently of the subject it can be an external and internal object conditioned to mastering ontogenesis.

Such a two-way approach to language is different from language activity sharply differs from cognitive manifestations.

Language mechanisms are not only the structure of thought it is a matter of how the structure is manifested in the form of characters considered together with Therefore, speech within the framework of cognitive linguistics and "mental" features in their formation and manifestation is studied. Research in cognitive linguistics cognitive mechanisms characteristic of a person as a whole, and this issues of categorization and conceptualization of mechanisms enables learning .

Because Cognitive Linguistics studies language phenomena with meaning and from the point of view of the human cognitive prism in the study of reference approaches and the lexical composition of the language is semiotic of human cognition is interpreted as the result of the condition related to the parameter.

The emergence of cognitive linguistics in the late 80s defined, and sometimes in 1989 by the International Association for Cognitive Linguistics organized by the organizer René Dirven and in Deisburg with the publication of the materials of the symposium participants will be connected. The emergence of the materials of the collection is the understanding of the language and to it is new (inextricably linked with the ideas of cognitive sciences). caused the emergence of the approach. When language is considered as a cognitive or cognitive-processual phenomenon, the main emphasis is on the world of language, began to focus on providing information about existence (3, 158) and it is such when transmitting information, it is integrated with the process of processing it in thinking construction of speech, organization and information to a perfect level a multifaceted process of bringing and transferring it to the communicative process made it possible to look at the quality of the product. Such an approach to language Today, a new direction in the science of linguistics is Cognitive Linguistics gave rise to it. The field of study of cognitive linguistics is clearly at its limit despite not having, until recent years, it has cognitive showing lexicology, different types of cognitive grammar and different directions of cognitive discourse research have emerged. On the other hand, in semantics, its cognitive is a prototype fields such as semantics, conceptual semantics, and frame semantics are intensive we can see that it is developing. And finally, today to date, in the study of a number of linguistic problems from a cognitive point of view it was possible to get new conclusions. First of all, now to conceptualization and categorization; in understanding the universe the reflection of the landscape in the language; correlative forms of language; language relationship of structures with cognitive structures, phrases.

There are several published in Russian and Uzbek linguistics related to the problem we can see in articles . In our opinion, the tasks of cognitive linguistics are:

- 1) in man determining the role of language in the emergence of knowledge;
- 2) the universe and in it categorization of things (forming concepts and dividing them into types); conceptualization (formation of concepts) and (nomination) understand processes;

3) between the conceptual system and the language system determine the relationship;

4) linguistic and cognitive (conceptual) world is to solve problems related to images.

So, in cognitive linguistics, language is the world of man and man appears as a means of expressing attitude. At this point, to the concepts of "cognitive linguistics" and "cognitive grammar". The word "cognitive" is English "cognize - to know, understand, is derived from the words "to understand", and this field is only knowledge in philosophy not limited to the theory, but connecting language with thinking (consciousness) and his psychological, biological and neurophysiological aspects of its formation deep scientific connection with social, cultural and linguistic phenomena researches.

According to Safarov, the task of cognitive linguistics is language acquisition and retention of knowledge, practical use and transfer of language, in general, thinking about the language system and structure as a reflection of the human brain

is an in-depth scientific research in connection with .

A. Abduazizov claims that the formation, transmission of speech, The brain is the center of complex phenomena such as conscious storage in memory carried out through neurons. The form of different units in the language different understandings, concepts, frames by differentiating the content using the national-cultural and social characteristics of each nation or ethnos Phonological tools are of great help in determining its uniqueness.

Human language is "sound, ", and it is great at creating content due to its importance being studied in cognitive phonetics and phonology recognizing that it is the main component of cognitive linguistics must In contemporary linguistics, the cognitive direction is lexical-semantic is closely related to level analysis, according to which the language is general information in the form of a cognitive weapon, along with being a cognitive mechanism performing the task of transmitting and changing its presentation, using code is also a symbol system.

In cognitive linguistics, the cognitive structure characteristic of a person and the mechanisms of complete acquisition of information are studied with the help of methods.

Professor D. Ashurova in his article of cognitive linguistics goals and tasks, current issues awaiting their solution shows . In particular, which is being formed in the present era cognitive phonology, cognitive grammar of cognitive

linguistics, new directions such as cognitive lexicology and cognitive semantics have emerged it is noted that he has arrived. Phrases based on cognitive approach, language categorization and conceptualization of units, language and concepts such as knowledge of the world will have new interpretations. Cognitive frame, script, script from the system of basic concepts of linguistics, categorization, concept, conceptualization, cognitive structure, Such as cognitive metaphors are taking place. This is the main direction research methods include analysis based on frames, modeling (cognitive mapping), such as conceptual analysis.

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